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ASSESSMENT OF THE PSYCHOLOGICAL STATE OF PREGNANT WOMEN WITH COVID-19 COMPLICATED BY THE DEVELOPMENT OF MULTIPLE ORGAN DYSFUNCTION SYNDROME AND ICU SYNDROME

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ABSTRACT

This article studies the psychological state of pregnant women with COVID-19 complicated by developing multiple organ dysfunction syndromes (MODS) and intensive care unit syndrome. 3080 pregnant women infected with SARS-CoV-2 during the COVID-19 pandemic in the maternity ward of the "Republican Specialized Infectious Diseases Hospital Zangiota-1" from December 2020 to January 01, 2022. During the study period, 22.0% of pregnant women with COVID-19 pneumonia needed intensive care in intensive care units. The frequency of cases with the development of MODS was 9.0% in the total analytical sample. Most deaths were noted among women with a highly severe course and mixed pathology of the psycho-emotional state - 44 cases. At baseline, 56.6% of women experienced stress, 26.7% had anxiety disorders, and 16.7% (113 out of 677) them had depression. In the postpartum period, combinations of stress, anxiety and depression were identified in 46.1% (312 out of 677) of cases, which was typical for women with preterm labor and miscarriages. Pregnant women in the third trimester with COVID-19 were most susceptible to MODS.

Keywords: COVID-19, pneumonia, pregnancy, psycho-emotional disorders, anxiety, depression, stress, resuscitation and intensive care, multiple organ dysfunction syndromes.

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ОЦЕНКА ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО СОСТОЯНИЯ БЕРЕМЕННЫХ С COVID-19, ОСЛОЖНЕННЫХ РАЗВИТИЕМ ПОЛИОРГАННОЙ НЕДОСТАТОЧНОСТИ И СИНДРОМА ПАЛАТЫ ИНТЕНСИВНОЙ ТЕРАПИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная статья посвящена изучению психологического состояния беременных женщин с COVID-19, осложненным развитием полиорганной недостаточности (ПОН) и синдрома палаты интенсивной терапии. 3080 беременных женщин, инфицированных SARS-CoV-2 во время пандемии COVID-19 в условиях родильного отделения «Республиканской специализированной инфекционной больницы Зангиота-1» с декабря 2020 года по 01 января 2022 года. За исследуемый период в интенсивной терапии в отделениях реанимации нуждались 22,0% беременных женщин с пневмонией COVID-19. Частота случаев с развитием ПОН составила 9,0% в общей аналитической выборке. Большинство летальных исходов отмечено среди женщин с крайне тяжелым течением и смешанной патологией психоэмоционального состояния – 44 случая. Исходно стресс испытывали 56,6% женщин, тревожные расстройства – 26,7%, и депрессивные состояния – 16,7% (113 из 677) случаев. В постродовом периоде сочетания стресса, тревоги и депрессии были выявлены в 46,1% (312 из 677) случаев, что было характерно для женщин с преждевременными родами и выкидышами. Беременные на третьем триместре с COVID-19 оказались наиболее сильно подвержены к ПОН.

Ключевые слова: COVID-19, пневмония, беременность, психоэмоциональные расстройства, тревога, депрессия, стресс, реанимация и интенсивная терапия, полиорганная недостаточность.

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КЎП АЪЗОЛАР ЕТИШМОВЧИЛИГИ ВА ИНТЕНСИВ ТЕРАПИЯ СИНДРОМИ РИВОЖЛАНИШИ БИЛАН АСОРАТЛАНГАН COVID-19 БИЛАН КАСАЛЛАНГАН ҲОМИЛАДОР АЁЛЛАРНИНГ ПСИХОЛОГИК ҲОЛАТИНИ БАҲОЛАШ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақола кўп аъзолар етишмовчилиги ва интенсив терапия синдроми ривожланиши билан асоратланган COVID-19 билан касалланган ҳомиладор аёлларнинг психологик ҳолатини ўрганишга бағишланган. 2020-йилнинг декабридан 2022-йил 01-январига қадар COVID-19 пандемияси даврида SARS-CoV-2 инфекциясини юқтирган ва "Зангиота-1 Республика ихтисослаштирилган юқумли касалликлар шифохонаси" туғруқ бўлимида даволанган 3080 нафар ҳомиладор аёл. Тадқиқот даврида COVID-19 пневмонияси билан касалланган ҳомиладор аёлларнинг 22,0% реанимация бўлимларида интенсив терапияга мухтож эди. Кўп аъзолар етишмовчилиги ривожланиши билан ҳолатларнинг умумий тахлилий намунада 9,0%-ни ташкил этди. Ўлим ҳолатларининг аксарияти ўта оғир кечадиган ва психо-эмоционал ҳолатнинг аралаш патологияси бўлган аёллар орасида қайд этилган – 44-та ҳолат. Дастлабки ҳолатга кўра, аёлларнинг 56,6% эмоционал стрессни бошдан кечирган, 26,7% ташвишли касалликларга дуч келган ва 16,7% депрессияга учраган. Туғруқдан кейинги даврда стресс ҳолат, ташвиш ва депрессиянинг комбинацияси 46,1% ҳолларда (677 тадан 312 тасида) аниқланган, бу эрта туғилиш ва абортлар билан аёллар учун хосдир. COVID-19 билан учинчи триместрдаги ҳомиладор аёллар кўп аъзолар етишмовчилигига кўпроқ мойил бўлган.

Калит сўзлар: COVID-19, пневмония, ҳомиладорлик, психоэмоционал касалликлар, ташвиш, депрессия, стресс, реанимация ва интенсив терапия, кўп аъзолар етишмовчилиги.

Introduction

The emergence of intensive care unit syndrome (ICUS) and post-intensive care syndrome (PICS) is a consequence of patients on prolonged artificial ventilation or the development of multiple organ dysfunction (MOD) and is the most difficult problem of modern disaster medicine. These syndromes appeared relatively recently as nosological forms of pathologies covering any consequences of prolonged hospitalization in an intensive care unit (ICU) [1-4].

Highlighting ICUS and PICS into separate nosological forms, including psychological, cognitive and physical disorders (among others, polyneuropathy, respiratory dysfunction, muscle and joint atrophy, etc.), is necessary today also because they have become acute, associated with a long stay of patients with COVID-19 pneumonia in ICU and their subsequent rehabilitation in the post-acute period [1, 2, 5, 6].

The number of patients surviving ICU admission is increasing, and treating PICS is a major problem [5, 7, 8]. This problem is particularly acute in pregnant and laboring women with COVID-

19 pneumonia, in whom several psychosomatic and cognitive factors will be mutually aggravated. Screening and treatment for these disorders is increasingly common, but no single method is effective. At the same time, introducing special measures for preventing and treating MOD and ICU syndrome is a complex task that should consider important medical and technical requirements of intensive care units [6, 7, 9-14].

This article presents the results of a study of the psychological state of pregnant and parturient women with COVID-19 complicated by the development of PON and ICU syndrome.

Material and Methods.

The basis of the study was the results of the examination and treatment of 3080 pregnant women and young mothers infected with SARS-CoV-2 during the COVID-19 pandemic in the maternity ward of the "Zangiota-1 Republican Specialized Infectious Hospital" from December 2020 to January 01, 2022.

Most women (48.0%; 1478 of 3080) were in the age range of 26-30 years, and most women (84.0%; 2586 of 3080) had no history of miscarriage. In terms of the number of pregnancies in the history of miscarriage, cases with two (31.0%; 956 of 3080) and one pregnancy (27.5%; 847 of 3080) in the history of miscarriage were the most common. Only 5.9% (183 of 3080) of pregnant women were primiparous. At the time of hospital admission, 889 of 3080 women (28.9%) were in their first trimester of pregnancy (<13 weeks gestation), 1,056 women (34.3%) in their second trimester (13-27 weeks gestation), and most of all, 1,135 women (36.8%) in their third trimester (≥ 28 weeks gestation).

According to the international criteria for evaluating the severity of infection, COVID-19, an intermediate course of pneumonia, was diagnosed in the vast majority of pregnant women (64.3%; 1980 out of 3080). The clinical presentation of pregnant women with COVID-19 infection was bilateral pneumonia in 48.0% (1478 of 3080). According to MSCT, the majority (60.0%; 1,848 of 3,080) of patients had up to 50% lung lesions.

Extragenital diseases were diagnosed in 1232 of 3080 (40.0%) patients. They were represented by: vegetovascular dystonia, various degrees of hypertension, chronic bronchitis, tonsillitis, chronic pyelonephritis, chronic gastritis, colitis, pancreatitis, autoimmune thyroiditis, metabolic syndrome, obesity, and myopia. There was a combination of different diseases in 943 patients. History of gynecological diseases: cervical ectopy, inflammatory diseases of the uterus and its appendages, ovarian tumors and tumor-like masses, uterine myoma, ectopic pregnancy, and infertility of different genesis were in 914 patients.

The evaluation and assessment of the severity of psycho-emotional disorders were performed using the GTR-7 Anxiety Disorder Rating Scale, the IES-6 Posttraumatic Stress Disorder Rating Scale (PTSD), and the PHQ-9 Depression Rating Scale. Conjoint psycho-emotional pathology was diagnosed using a special combined PHQ-ADS scale, which was the sum of the scores of the PHQ-9 and GTR-7 questionnaires (maximum score was 48, and a combination of PTSD, anxiety and depression was revealed at 20 points or more).

Results. During the study period, 22.0% (677 of 3080) of pregnant women with COVID-19 pneumonia required intensive care in intensive care units, of which the vast majority (72.4%; 490 of 677) were cases with a severe clinical course of COVID-19 (Figure 1, Table 2).

The frequency of cases with the development of multi-organ failure in COVID-19 was 41.0% (277 of 677) among resuscitating pregnant patients and 9.0% (277 of 3080) in the overall analytic sample according to the study period (January 7 to December 26, 2021).

Most cases of MODS in pregnancy (75.4%; 209 of 277) with COVID-19 pneumonia were women in the third trimester of pregnancy with a baseline severe COVID-19 clinical presentation (61.4%; 170 of 277) (Table 2). The mortality rate in the ICU was 9.4% (64 of 677). In this pattern, most fatalities were among women with an extremely severe course and mixed psycho-emotional pathology - 44 cases.

Picture 1.

Distribution of intensive care pregnant women with COVID-19 pneumonia by severity

Table 1.

ICU outcomes in pregnant women with COVID-19 and psycho-emotional disorders

	Source	Recovery	Lethality
ICU (n=677)			
Medium Severe	113	111	2
Severe	490	472	18
Extremely severe	74	30	44
Total	677	613 (90,6%)	64 (9,4%)
Patients with MODS (n=277)			
Medium Severe	12	10	2
Severe	209	191	18
Extremely severe	56	12	44
Total	277	213 (76,9%)	64 (23,1%)

The results of the detection of psycho-emotional disorders in patients using special questionnaire scales showed that PTSD was initially experienced by 56.6% (383 of 677) of women, generalized anxiety disorders were noted in 26.7% (181 of 677), and depressive states were diagnosed in 16.7% (113 of 677) of cases (Table 1).

In the postpartum period, as assessed by the combined PHQ-ADS scale, combinations of PTSD, anxiety, and depression were found in 46.1% (312 of 677) of cases, which was characteristic of women with severe and extremely severe COVID-19, preterm birth, miscarriage, and perinatal mortality.

Table 2.

Distribution of resuscitated pregnant women with COVID-19 pneumonia according to psycho-emotional findings

Medium Severe COVID-19 (n=113)	Severe degree COVID-19 (n=490)	Extremely severe. COVID-19 (n=74)	Total (n=677)
PTSD (IES-6)			
78 (69,0%)	266 (54,3%)	39 (52,7%)	383 (56,6%)
35 (31,0%)	224 (45,7%)	35 (47,3%)	294 (43,4%)
Anxiety (ГTP-7)			
20 (17,7%)	140 (28,6%)	21 (28,4%)	181 (26,7%)
93 (82,3%)	350 (71,4%)	53 (71,6%)	496 (73,3%)
Depression (PHQ-9)			

15 (13,3%)	84 (17,1%)	14 (18,9%)	113 (16,7%)
98 (86,7%)	406 (82,9%)	60 (81,1%)	564 (83,3%)
PTSD + anxiety + depression (PHQ-ADS)			
44 (38,9%)	229 (46,7%)	39 (52,7%)	312 (46,1%)
69 (61,1%)	261 (53,3%)	35 (47,3%)	365 (53,9%)

Analysis of the literature showed that the pathogenesis of psycho-emotional and cognitive disorders in COVID-19 is directly related to severe respiratory failure with the development of hypoxic and hemic hypoxia. Besides, it was proved that manifestations of psychological and emotional disorders arising against the background of COVID-19 are associated with the stressful environment due to the pandemic and the direct influence of the virus on the nervous system of patients.

It was determined that in the presence of severe psycho-emotional disturbances in pregnant women with COVID-19, the efficacy of protocols for the main directions of etiotropic and pathogenetic treatment (coagulopathy correction, respiratory and antibacterial therapy) directly depends on an appropriate regime of psychosocial support of pregnancy.

Analysis of the questionnaire scales used to assess psycho-emotional disorders in women with COVID-19 and MODS during the postpartum period showed that PTSD symptoms were pronounced in the third trimester of pregnancy, amidst higher rates of perinatal mortality, cesarean section, prolonged stay on the ventilator and in the ICU.

Responses with high scores on the combined PHQ-ADS scale were statistically significantly higher in women in the 2nd and 3rd trimesters of pregnancy than in the 1st trimester (Figure 5.6).

Thus, combined psycho-emotional disorders with pronounced symptoms of PTSD, anxiety, and depression against the background of pregnancy and COVID-19 pneumonia scored above thresholds on the PHQ-ADS scale (≥ 19 points) and were also characterized by the development of MDOS.

Note:

- 1) I think about what happened against my will;
- 2) I am constantly wary and keep expecting something bad to happen;
- 3) some things make me think about what happened all the time;
- 4) I am still overwhelmed with heavy feelings about what happened;
- 5) I try not to think about what happened;
- 6) I find it difficult to concentrate on anything.

Figure 2. Prevalence of elevated PTSD symptoms associated with COVID-19 pneumonia and PON confirmed in pregnant women (n=277)

• ICUS risk factors were commonly recognized predictors that were uniform for maternity unit ICU patients, viz:

• ICU environment (noise, sleep disturbance, patients' awareness of the severity of their condition) influenced 234 (84.5%) patients;

• vegetative disorders and polyneuropathy (TRB, delirium) were not eliminated in 155 (55,9%) patients;

• metabolic and hypoxic disorders (diabetes mellitus, metabolic syndrome) were noted in 103 (37.2%) patients;

• an abundance of diagnostic and therapeutic procedures influenced the psyche of almost all conscious patients;

• impact of various pharmacological agents on patients' psyche (sedatives, antidepressants, etc.), adverse drug reactions were noted in 5 (1.8%) patients.

• Early signs of ICUS were verbal agitation (165/59.5%), unexplained depression (176/63.5%), inadequate requests or actions (56/20.2%);

Measures that contribute to the prevention and timely treatment of SOIT, we systematized as follows:

- Preoperative contact with the patient, if possible, is necessary;
- Proactive analgesia and sedation;
- Sedation and tranquilization;
- Reduction and consolidation of therapeutic activities;
- Special attention to patients on prolonged lung ventilation;
- Involvement of a psychotherapist if necessary;

Note: 1) lack of interest in events; 2) indifference, listlessness; 3) insomnia or drowsiness; 4) fatigue/lack of energy; 5) lack of appetite or overeating; 6) feeling like a failure; 7) difficulty concentrating; 8) slowness and lethargy; 9) suicidal thoughts or self-harm; 10) increased nervous excitability, restlessness or irritability; 11) inability to cope with anxiety; 12) excessive worrying about different things; 13) inability to relax; 14) extreme anxiety "can't find my place"; 15) easily succumbing to feelings of anxiety or irritability; 16) fear of something scary.

Figure 3. Prevalence of symptoms of mixed mental disorders confirmed in pregnant women with COVID-19 pneumonia and MODS (n=277)

After intensive care patients' recovery and discharge from the hospital (n=613), an individual rehabilitation program was made for each case, taking into account risk factors. Further, based on monthly questioning of patients (in-patient call or by phone) by IES-6 scale (for PTSD assessment) and combined PHQ-ADS scale (for anxiety/depression assessment), the levels of rehabilitation in the groups of moderate (n=111), severe (n=472) and extremely severe (n=30) COVID-19 pneumonia

course were studied. The index of rehabilitation level was also studied in the group of patients with MODC (n=277).

Patients were rehabilitated if they scored less than 19 points on the IES-6 scale (exclusion of posttraumatic stress) and scored less than 2 on the combined PHQ-ADS scale, in which anxiety and depressive syndrome were excluded).

Figure 4. Cumulative rehabilitation curve of perinatal women with COVID-19 pneumonia and psycho-emotional disorders after treatment in the ICU (n=613)

Figure 5. Cumulative rehabilitation rates of pregnant women with COVID-19 and psychiatric disorders after treatment in the ICU

Thus, Fig. 4 shows that by 8 months after the completion of intensive therapy for the main pathology, COVID-19 pneumonia, all women were rehabilitated and completely cured of psycho-emotional disorders. At the same time, at 5 and 6 months, half of those who continued rehabilitation completed it, i.e. the maximum effect was obtained 5 months after the start of rehabilitation.

Table 4.

Rehabilitation rates in perinatal women with COVID-19 pneumonia and psycho-emotional disorders after treatment in the ICU

Time, months.	Finished rehabilitation	Discharged from rehabilitation	Continued rehabilitation
Moderate-to-severe group COVID-19			
0	0	0	111
2	10	0	111
3	47	2	101
4	47	5	52
Severe Current Group COVID-19 (n=472)			
0	0	0	472
2	2	0	472
3	8	0	470
4	86	7	462
5	190	8	369
6	100	10	171
7	55	5	61
8	1	0	1
Group of extremely severe currents COVID-19 (n=30)			
0	0	0	30
5	4	0	30
6	6	0	26
7	2	1	20
8	16	1	17
MODS (n=213)			
0	0	0	213
5	77	3	213
6	106	4	133
7	4	2	13
8	11	0	11

The results of psycho-emotional disorders rehabilitation in the group with an intermediate course among women treated in the ICU were better than in the group with severe and extremely severe COVID-19 pneumonia (Table 4, Figure 5). Thus, while moderate cases completed rehabilitation within 4 months after hospital discharge, severe cases completed rehabilitation only by 8 months after discharge, and highly severe cases were characterized by the fact that more than half of them still continued rehabilitation by that date (Table 4 and Figure 5).

Figure 6. Comparison of rehabilitative rates of total resuscitation (n=613) and pregnant women with MODC (n=213) against COVID-19 and psycho-emotional disorders

After polyorgan failure and recovery, 213 women with psycho-emotional disorders in the form of PTSD, anxiety, and depressive syndrome successfully completed their rehabilitation course later than the average times typical for general resuscitation patients (Figure 6). Thus, the effect of MODC on the worsening of the clinical picture of psycho-emotional disorders and prolongation of the rehabilitation period due to ICU syndrome was shown.

Conclusions. The incidence of cases with the development of multiple organ failure in COVID-19 was 41.0% among resuscitated pregnant patients and 9.0% in the overall analytic sample. Intensive care in intensive care units is needed in 22.0% of pregnant women with COVID-19 pneumonia, among whom the vast majority (72.4%) are cases with a severe clinical course of COVID-19.

The rehabilitation period in women after pregnancy and delivery against the background of COVID-19 infection and experiencing psycho-emotional disorders in the form of PTSD, anxiety and depression, was prolonged to 8 months with worse rates after COVID-19 pneumonia in an extremely severe form and in cases of MODC development.

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